

Research Training Needs Assessment of Teachers

Mark Donnel D Viernes^{1,2*}

¹College of Education, Western Philippines University, Puerto Princesa City, Philippines, ²College of Education, University of the Philippines Diliman, Quezon City, Philippines. *Corresponding Author's Email: markdonnel.viernes@wpu.edu.ph

Abstract

The Napsan NHS and ES have not produced any research output, at least, since 2023. This is despite the Department of Education's mandate in research-based instruction and management policies. Thus, this study examined the research training needs of DepEd teachers in Napsan, a community in Puerto Princesa, Philippines. A quantitative cross-sectional survey was conducted among 19 teachers from elementary, junior high, and senior high schools using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. The survey assessed competencies grouped under training themes such as Fundamentals, Research Methods, Instrument Development, Qualitative Data Analysis, Quantitative Data Analysis, Referencing, and Post-Research Activities using the P-R-I-O-R-I-Ty Framework. Findings revealed that while teachers consider research skills to be very important, their self-rated proficiency remains only moderate across all areas. The discrepancy was most pronounced in Instrument Development, which emerged as the highest priority for improvement, followed by both Quantitative and Qualitative Data Analysis. Follow-up community feedback further confirmed that the proposed training areas are relevant and require prompt action. The study recommends implementing professional development programs focused on practical research skills following the aforementioned priorities, creating continuous support systems such as professional learning communities, and the need for technical advisory partners to cultivate a vibrant research culture among teachers in Napsan.

Keywords: Assessment, Extension, Professional, Teachers.

Introduction

Research plays a critical role in advancing innovation and effectiveness in education, particularly through the essential contributions of teachers who shape students' learning experiences, which benefit the community. Napsan is a developing barangay in the western part of Palawan, Philippines, home to two institutions: Napsan National High School (NNHS) and Napsan Elementary School (NES). Together, these schools accommodate a combined teaching faculty of 32 — 24 in the NNHS and 8 in the NES. Despite their considerable teaching population, these institutions have not produced any research output in 2023, based on reports from the division office. This alarming situation signifies a pressing need for interventions to build the research capacities of the faculty in these schools.

The absence of research output in Napsan is not merely an administrative gap; it reflects a missed opportunity to address the unique educational and socioeconomic challenges of the barangay. The geographic isolation, limited infrastructure, and

reliance on the agriculture and fishing livelihoods of Napsan created distinct barriers to student engagement and access. For instance, students may face irregular attendance due to seasonal family labor demands or difficulties traveling to school during the monsoon season. Without locally rooted research, teachers risk relying on generic pedagogical strategies that fail to account for such realities (1, 2). Training teachers in research methodologies would empower them to investigate these contextual issues systematically, design interventions that fit their needs (e.g., flexible learning schedules or community-integrated curricula), and advocate for evidence-based resource allocation from local government units.

While teachers are often trained in pedagogical theories, the lack of a research culture in these schools in Napsan limits their ability to adapt these theories to their classrooms (3). Research training would enable educators to critically evaluate the best teaching methods for their students, particularly in

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

(Received 08th March 2025; Accepted 21st June 2025; Published 20th October 2025)

resource-constrained environments. For example, how can project-based learning be adapted for a classroom with intermittent electricity? Can local ecological knowledge be integrated into science lessons to enhance their relevance? If we equip teachers with skills in action research—a practical, iterative approach to solving classroom problems—teachers at Napsan could transform everyday challenges into opportunities for innovation so that teaching practices align with students' lived experiences.

There is no shortage of written accounts documenting low research skills among teachers in the Philippines. Studies have illustrated the challenges faced by many teachers, including lack of proficiency in key research competencies and insufficient access to professional development programs (4-6). These obstacles persist despite the Department of Education's (DepEd) emphasis on the importance of research in improving educational quality. Policies such as DepEd Order No. 16, s. 2017, which encourages teacher-led investigations into instructional strategies, and DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2010, which institutionalizes research as a core activity and emphasizes the critical role of research in addressing educational gaps (7, 8). The Basic Education Research Agenda (DepEd Order No. 43, s. 2015) further prioritizes themes such as teaching methods and child protection, whereas the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 integrates research into teachers' professional development (9, 10).

Though it is clear that there is a persistent problem with the research capability of the teachers, several literature stress the importance of conducting a training needs assessment (TNA) prior to implementing any educational program (11-13). A research TNA is an essential tool for addressing these challenges to provide a systematic approach to identifying the current state (what is) and desired state (what should be) (14). Frameworks like the Borich model (15) have been widely used in TNA studies to analyze training needs, especially for teachers. Borich operationally defined 'need' as the discrepancy score between the proficiency and importance of the competencies – which has been heavily adopted by succeeding researchers. However, traditional models like Borich's have faced criticism in several studies (16-19). The Borich

model calculates discrepancy scores by combining self-reported proficiency with group mean importance ratings. However, it has notable limitations. For example, it relies on arithmetic means derived from ordinal data, which is problematic since such data often do not meet the assumptions required for calculating means. To elaborate, responses at per item level are inherently ordinal; thus, computing for the arithmetic mean would be inappropriate and not meaningful. However, the summated or averaged responses in a Likert scale (collection of Likert items) produce an interval level of data (20); such data are appropriate for mean computation and parametric tests.

The aforementioned limitation on Borich's model was noticed by some researchers, and the Ranked Discrepancy Model (RDM) was proposed (18). In this model, the arithmetic mean was not used; instead, a frequency distribution of positive ranks (where proficiency levels are rated higher than importance levels), negative ranks (where proficiency levels are rated lower than importance levels), and tied ranks were utilized. The frequency of each rank per competency will then be converted into percentages and multiplied by the following weights: -1 (for negative rank), 0 (for tied rank), and 1 (for positive rank). Finally, the sum of these weighted percentages (Ranked Discrepancy Score) will serve as an indicator of need, i.e., if the sum is a negative percentage, then there is a need for intervention for that competency. However, upon closely examining the steps, they are neglecting one concept. To illustrate, we can simulate two cases of ratings. The first case is where a client rated a specific competency as very essential (equivalent to 5) and rated his proficiency as above average (equivalent to 4); since the proficiency score is lower than the importance score, it will be weighted as -1. In the second case, if another client rated the same competency as very essential (equivalent to 5) and rated proficiency as very poor (equivalent to 1), it will still be weighted as -1. Clearly, the second case has a different magnitude of need than the second one, but this model will still treat them the same and ignore the discrepancy between them. Therefore, the approach failed to account for the "individual client-level magnitude" of need.

The solution to the problem noticed in Borich's model is not to deviate from using the arithmetic mean but to analyze the need in the scale level instead of per item (21). To address the areas where Borich's model and the RDM fall short, the current study introduces an innovative framework to assess the research training needs of the teachers in Napsan. Specifically, it seeks to ascertain the inter-relatedness of the competencies composing a training theme; to measure the perceived importance and current proficiency of various research training themes among the teachers; to classify training themes such as critically needed, moderately needed, surplus, and strengths; to

identify priority research training as a whole and as subgroups; and to validate findings through community feedback.

Methodology

Research Framework

A quantitative multiphase cross-sectional survey was utilized to determine the research training needs of DepEd teachers in Napsan. The study follows a positivist paradigm, as it seeks to provide empirical evidence on training needs to ensure that the findings are grounded in observable and verifiable data.

Figure 1: Research Framework of the Study

As there were limitations on the available framework for training needs assessment, the study integrated several approaches from the literature to organize the P-R-I-O-R-I-Ty Framework (Figure 1). One of the highlights of this study is the introduction of this framework, which demonstrates a structured approach to training needs assessment. Furthermore, this framework is not limited to teachers' training needs but can also be applied to other fields, such as healthcare, corporate, agriculture, or any organizational capacity building, where competency assessment and enhancement are essential. The following discusses how this framework was utilized to investigate the research training needs of DepEd teachers in Napsan.

Phase 1. Preparation of Relevant Competencies: Forty-two competencies were identified through a comprehensive review of relevant literature (Table 1). Competencies must be grouped to identify training themes. Researchers must have a theoretical or conceptual basis that outlines how competencies should be grouped (e.g., based on expert judgment, literature review, or prior research). In the current study, the forty-two competencies were nested under seven training themes aligned with the literature review. The groups include Fundamentals, which covers foundational research skills; Research Methods, which encompasses the design and methodology of studies; Instrument Development, which focuses on the creation and validation of

research tools; Qualitative Data Analysis, addressing the interpretation of non-numeric data; Quantitative Data Analysis, covering statistical and numerical techniques; Referencing, which involves citation practices and tools; and Post-Research, which emphasizes dissemination activities such as publishing and presenting research findings.

Phase 2. Research Instrument Design: A 5-point Likert-type scale questionnaire is created, each competency represented by a statement. Respondents assess each competency on two scales: one for perceived importance and another for current proficiency. The discrepancy between these ratings serves as an indicator of 'need' (15). The two-part format (proficiency-importance) of the needs assessment questionnaire introduced by Borich was adapted for this framework.

The Proficiency Scale responses were described as follows: 1 – Not Proficient at All (lack this competency entirely); 2 – Slightly Proficient (have basic knowledge but need further development); 3 – Moderately Proficient (can perform tasks independently but could improve further); 4 – Very Proficient (highly skilled and meet most job demands of research work); 5 – Extremely Proficient (have exceptional mastery and can mentor others).

On the other hand, the Importance Scale responses were as follows: 1 – Not Important at All (no relevance on role as teacher-researcher); 2 – Slightly Important (has limited relevance and minimal impact); 3 – Moderately Important (somewhat useful but not essential); 4 – Very Important (will improve ability to conduct or support research effectively); 5 – Extremely Important (critical for success as teacher-researcher).

Adult learners, especially professionals, tend not to pay attention to learning skills that they do not feel necessary for their work (22). Thus, asking about each competency's perceived importance would make the training more relevant and address the most pertinent skills to their professional needs.

Ideally, proficiency should be measured objectively, as this approach provides reliable and precise assessments of skill levels. However, objective measurement often imposes significant challenges on respondents. It can feel like taking a formal test, which might increase respondent fatigue and disengagement, particularly when assessing broad

and diverse skills like those required for research. Additionally, such assessments tend to be lengthy and time-consuming, which can further strain respondents' participation and compliance.

As an alternative, researchers have often turned to self-assessment Likert-scale surveys. This approach relies on the trust that respondents can accurately evaluate their own competencies. While self-assessments have limitations, such as potential biases or inaccuracies, they have been shown to be a feasible and effective tool for measuring adult skills, particularly when the respondents are mature and experienced. Adults, like teachers, are generally better assessors of their own skills compared to younger individuals due to their greater experience and metacognitive awareness (23).

The aggregated averages of competencies served as the score for the individual measurement of importance and proficiency in each training theme (20, 21). Thus, averages of Likert items were not interpreted, but the Likert scale of each training theme; this addresses the limitation mentioned earlier on Borich's model.

Phase 3. Intentional Sampling: Organizations are inherently composed of diverse factions—groups that arise based on functions, specializations, or other demographics. This diversity means that each subgroup tends to face unique challenges and, therefore, generally requires more fitted training solutions rather than a uniform approach unless a specific competency is lacking across the board. To further refine the analysis of the current study, respondents are categorized based on their departments (Elementary, Junior High School, Senior High School), career stages (Early, Mid, and Late career), and sex (Male, Female). Categorizing respondents is crucial to uncover variations in training needs within the organization so that training priorities are not 'blindly' generalized but built from the unique requirements of subgroups (24). The importance of subgroup analysis lies in its ability to identify specific needs so that certain groups requiring intensive training are not overlooked simply because other groups are proficient in the same areas.

Due to ethical considerations, voluntary (convenience) sampling was employed to maximize response rates while noting this as a limitation for

broader generalizability. All 32 DepEd teachers at Napsan (24 at NNHS, 8 at NES) were invited, and 19 (59%) voluntarily participated. Four were teaching senior high school students (21%), nine were teaching junior high school students (47%), and six were elementary school teachers (32%). In terms of years of service, there are seven beginning teachers (0 – 4 years), six mid-career teachers (5 – 9 years), and six veteran teachers (at least 10 years). Unsurprisingly, there were more female teachers (79%) than male teachers (21%) in our sample because teaching is a female-dominated profession in the Philippines (25, 26).

Phase 4. Optimization of Training Themes: For large organizations, using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to confirm the groupings of competencies is ideal to ensure that the training themes are both statistically robust and conceptually meaningful; this is due to the fact that CFA is a large-sample technique (27). However, in our current case, where a low sample size (less than 200) was obtained (28, 29), an alternative statistical tool

$$WDS = (ImpR - ProfR) \times Mean ImpR \quad [1]$$

Where Imp and ProfR are the importance ratings and proficiency ratings, respectively; the computed WDS served as the needs score for each respondent in each competency at this step.

Phase 5. Reveal Training Needs: As defined earlier, a need is when there is a discrepancy between current proficiency and perceived importance. Such pairing can be visually presented through a two-dimensional coordinate system (or plane), with the x-axis as the proficiency level and the y-axis as the importance levels (Figure 2). The training themes will be represented by a point with coordinates (x, y). In our case, x is the mean proficiency, and y is the mean importance. The x and y-axis start with the value 1, as the lowest pair of mean possible is (1,1). To add, since we are now relying on arithmetic mean, which considers every magnitude of difference between proficiency and the importance of a training theme, we avoided the limitation posed by the RDM model.

Training themes can be categorized into mutually exclusive groups such as critical need, moderate need, surplus, non-priority, and strength – as presented in the plane's five regions. To determine

should be utilized instead. Particularly, Cronbach's alpha (α) is a useful measure of internal consistency, especially in situations when the sample size or number of items is low but the scale is unidimensional (30). Particularly, training themes with $\alpha \geq 0.70$ suggest that competencies within the training theme are related to each other and, thus, statistically support the groupings of the competencies (31).

For training themes with low Alpha values, further analysis will be conducted to identify problematic competencies within the theme. Techniques such as item-rest correlation will help pinpoint competencies that do not align well with the rest of the competencies within the training theme (32). These competencies might be reassigned to different training themes or excluded altogether to improve the groupings of the competencies. A rule-of-thumb coefficient of at least 0.40 was suggested for a typical behavior questionnaire (33). Borich's way of computing weighted discrepancy score (WDS) was utilized, i.e.,

which category a training theme belongs to, simply plot the coordinates and spot which of the regions it corresponds to. This process of two-dimensional mapping has been heavily adapted from the performance-importance matrix (34).

Competencies in critical need and moderate need regions indicate that these are essential but currently lacking; thus, it is crucial to address them for effective performance. Particularly, training is critically needed if it has low proficiency-high importance pairs (35).

If a competency lies in the surplus region, this suggests that teachers possess strong proficiency in the area of lower importance, which represents a "surplus" that could be beneficial if needs shift but is currently not critical. Areas with high proficiency but lower importance have been identified as "excessive effort" that could be reallocated as needed (36).

Competencies in the strength region are where teachers perceive these as highly important but also possess high proficiency; these competencies are considered core strengths or highlights of the organization. Some researchers used a similar matrix approach in evaluating service quality,

labeling areas of high importance and proficiency as core competencies that support overall quality and consistency (37).

If competency is in a non-priority region, this indicates that it is neither a current need nor an area of strength; thus, it can be deprioritized. By identifying and deprioritizing areas with low importance and low performance, organizations can strategically allocate resources to more critical competencies (38).

Phase 6. Identification of Priority Areas: Training themes are ranked by effect size (omega squared)

$$\omega^2 = \frac{t^2 - 1}{t + n - 1} \quad [2]$$

Where t is the statistic for paired samples t-test and n is the sample size (39).

Chances are, a training theme might be only needed for a particular subgroup of the respondents, while other subgroups may require different training themes. Hence, a subgroup analysis will be beneficial in saving both time and resources. In this study, teachers were grouped by their department and by their length of service. Borich's way of computing weighted discrepancy scores (WDS) was utilized. The computed WDS served as the needs score for each individual in this subgroup analysis. Assumption checks revealed that the residuals were normally distributed within each group ($W \geq 0.94$, $p > .05$); however, homogeneity tests showed that not all training themes were homogenous. Thus, a parametric test, Welch's Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), was utilized.

Phase 7. Community Check: Once the competencies have been organized into training themes, they should be shared with the community for validation. This will not only enhance the credibility of the findings but also promote ownership and buy-in among stakeholders (40, 41). This is an opportunity for the respondents to develop a sense of commitment to the resulting project.

A follow-up survey questionnaire (Likert scale) has been distributed using an online survey software

from paired t-tests (importance levels vs proficiency levels) of each training theme to determine areas where the gap between perceived importance and proficiency is widest and most impactful. These parametric tests were employed since it was determined that the difference scores between pairs (importance vs. proficiency) are normally distributed for all training themes (Shapiro-Wilk $W \geq 0.91$, $p > 0.05$). Omega square (ω^2) is computed manually using the formula:

(Qualtrics) to the teachers of NES and NNHS; more than half of the target population (~59%) voluntarily participated in this survey. The questionnaire is composed of two sections: relevance and priority. In the relevance section, the respondents were asked to express their level of agreement (1 strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree) to the proposed needed training based on the result of Step 5. In the priority section, respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement on the order of training based on the priority analysis in Step 6.

Shapiro-Wilk test indicated that the averaged responses are not normally distributed, $W = 0.003$, $p < .001$; thus, succeeding analysis calls for a non-parametric test. The median responses for each training theme served as the agreement score in both sections (relevance and priority). The median for each theme was interpreted as follows: 1.00 – 1.50 Strongly Disagree; 1.51 – 2.50 Slightly Disagree; 2.51 – 3.50 Neither Disagree nor Agree; 3.51 – 4.50 Slightly Agree; 4.51 – 5.00 Strongly Agree (cf. (42)). A one-sample Wilcoxon sign test was also performed to determine whether the median response is significantly greater than 3.50 (Neither Disagree nor Agree) at a 0.01 significance level.

Results

Inter-Relatedness of Competencies within a Predefined Training Theme

Post-hoc test of internal consistency by computing Cronbach's α coefficient indicated that all competencies within the training themes are significantly interrelated, $\alpha \geq 0.70$ (Table 1). However, further analysis using the item-rest correlation, the competency "Preparing interview script/schedule" did not reach the 0.40 cut-off. Moreover, dropping this competency would improve the alpha value of the Instrument Development training theme to 0.87. It has been decided to place this competency under the Qualitative Data Analysis training theme since, conceptually, it is the next training theme related to it. The recalculated alpha value of Qualitative Data analysis training is 0.93, and the new item-rest correlation of the disputed competency is 0.63.

Perceived Importance and Proficiency of Various Research Training Themes

The respondents reported all training themes as very important ($3.51 \geq \bar{x} \geq 4.50$). In addition, they rated themselves as moderately proficient ($2.51 \geq \bar{x} \geq 3.50$) in all training themes (Table 2). Moreover, the proficiency scale in each training theme is rated lower than the importance scale.

Classification of Training Themes Based on Level of Needs

Upon plotting the training coordinate points (x, y) on the training categorization plane, all training themes

were mapped on the 'moderate need' region (Figure 2).

Priority Research Training as a Whole and Subgroup

As a whole, the results show that there is a significant deviation between the mean importance and proficiency scores in all training themes (Table 3). The computed ω^2 , which indicates the ranks of training themes, revealed that instrument development was the top training priority, followed by qualitative and quantitative data analysis. Training on Research methods was ranked at the lowest. Subgroup analysis indicated that there are no significant differences in the extent of need in all training themes if we group the teachers based on their department and years of service (Table 4).

Validating Findings through Community Feedback

In terms of relevance of the training themes presented in Table 2, the result showed that the median score is significantly higher than 3.50 (Table 5). Thus, the teachers at Napsan confirmed the need for these trainings. Similarly, the community expressed high agreement on the ranking of the training themes; this suggests that the community corroborated that instrument development was the most needed training, followed by quantitative analysis, qualitative analysis, post-research activities, fundamentals, and research methods.

Table 1: Research Competencies

Competency [with item-rest correlation]		Reference
Fundamentals $\alpha = 0.94$	1. Identifying research gaps [0.78]	(43-45)
	2. Formulating research questions (qualitative and quantitative). [0.75]	
	3. Selecting an appropriate theoretical or conceptual framework to guide the study [0.86]	
	4. Crafting hypotheses that are specific, measurable, and grounded in prior research [0.90]	
	5. Defining how variables will be measured or observed in the study [0.92]	
	6. Conducting a literature review [0.69]	
Research Methods	7. Selecting appropriate research designs (e.g., experimental, qualitative, mixed-methods) [0.62]	(43-45)

$\alpha = 0.94$	8. Utilizing qualitative research methodologies (e.g., grounded theory, phenomenology, ethnography) [0.92]	
	9. Utilizing quantitative research methodologies (e.g., experimental, observational) [0.89]	
	10. Utilizing mixed methods (e.g., exploratory, explanatory, embedded) [0.93]	
	11. Sampling and sample size determination [0.72]	
	12. Integrating research ethics based on the 2022 National Ethics Guidelines [0.86]	
Instrument Development $\alpha = 0.83$	13. Crafting instrument for measuring cognitive learning and affective domain [0.71]	(44, 46, 47)
	14. Writing purpose, scoring, administration, and psychometric properties of the instrument [0.56]	
	15. Pilot testing of the instrument/pilot interviews [0.78]	
	16. Validating and psychometric evaluation of the instrument [0.61]	
	17. Ensuring the test or scale is free from cultural, gender, or other biases using Item Differential Functioning [0.73]	
	18. Preparing interview script /schedule [0.38]***	
Qualitative Data Analysis $\alpha = 0.94$	19. Codifying and categorizing [0.78]	(48, 49)
	20. Conducting content analysis [0.80]	
	21. Analyzing interview data [0.83]	
	22. Analyzing focus group data [0.85]	
	23. Writing analytic memos about narrative and visual data [0.87]	
	24. Coding with qualitative data analysis software [0.86]	
Quantitative Data Analysis $\alpha = 0.95$	25. Interpreting statistical significance, effect size, and statistical power [0.89]	(39, 44, 50)
	26. Choosing the appropriate statistical test [0.88]	
	27. Performing and interpreting descriptive statistics (e.g., measures of central tendency, variability) [0.86]	
	28. Performing and interpreting tests of differences (e.g., t-test, ANOVA, chi-square) [0.81]	
	29. Performing and interpreting tests of associations (e.g., Pearson correlation, Spearman's rho) [0.86]	
	30. Performing and interpreting factor analysis (e.g., PCA, EFA, CFA) [0.88]	
	31. Citing references in APA format [0.58]	(51-54)
	32. Using citation tools such as Zotero and Mendeley [0.81]	
Referencing $\alpha = 0.91$	33. Automating reference extraction [0.86]	
	34. Navigating open-access resources [0.83]	
	35. Paraphrasing and summarizing sourced material [0.81]	
	36. Citing non-traditional sources [0.76]	
	37. Transforming completed research into a journal article [0.60]	(55-59)
	38. Presenting research at conferences [0.93]	
Post-Research $\alpha = 0.95$	39. Crafting infographics from the research output [0.84]	
	40. Writing Policy Briefs [0.90]	
	41. Data sharing and archiving (e.g., Figshare) [0.88]	
	42. Publishing processes in peer-reviewed journals [0.89]	

Notes: ***item low item-rest correlation, less than 0.40 cut-off

Figure 2: Training Theme Classification on Training Categorization Plane

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Importance and Proficiency Ratings

Training Themes	Importance Rating			Description	Proficiency Rating		
	Min. Max.	\bar{x}			Min. Max.	\bar{x}	
Fundamentals	3.17 – 5.00	4.07		Very Important	1.17 – 4.00	2.97	Moderately Proficient
Research Methods	3.17 – 5.00	4.06		Very Important	1.00 – 4.67	3.01	Moderately Proficient
Instrument Development	3.20 – 5.00	4.17		Very Important	1.00 – 4.20	3.01	Moderately Proficient
Qualitative Data Analysis	2.86 – 5.00	4.25		Very Important	1.14 – 4.00	3.04	Moderately Proficient
Quantitative Data Analysis	3.17 – 5.00	4.27		Very Important	1.00 – 4.33	2.97	Moderately Proficient
Referencing	3.00 – 5.00	4.18		Very Important	1.17 – 5.00	3.06	Moderately Proficient
Post-Research Activities	3.33 – 5.00	4.29		Very Important	1.00 – 5.00	3.04	Moderately Proficient

Table 3: Priority Analysis for Training Themes

Training Themes	Difference between \bar{x} Importance and Proficiency			
	t (df = 18)	p	ω^2	Priority Rank
Fundamentals	4.51	<.001	0.504	6

Research Methods	4.39	<.001	0.490	7
Instrument Development	5.42	<.001	0.599	1
Qualitative Data Analysis	4.87	<.001	0.545	3
Quantitative Data Analysis	4.96	<.001	0.554	2
Referencing	4.52	<.001	0.506	5
Post-Research Activities	4.55	<.001	0.509	4

Table 4: Subgroup Analysis of Training Themes by Department and Length of Service

Training Themes	By Department		By Length of Service	
	<i>F</i> (df1, df2)	<i>p</i>	<i>F</i> (df1, df2)	<i>p</i>
Fundamentals	0.34 (2, 8.60)	0.721	2.72 (3, 7.75)	0.160
Research Methods	1.05 (2, 8.13)	0.392	1.03 (3, 7.68)	0.431
Instrument Development	0.95 (2, 8.78)	0.424	0.73 (3, 7.16)	0.564
Qualitative Data Analysis	0.40 (2, 9.89)	0.679	3.98 (3, 7.20)	0.058
Quantitative Data Analysis	0.14 (2, 9.45)	0.874	1.33 (3, 7.62)	0.333
Referencing	0.68 (2, 9.74)	0.530	2.52 (3, 7.40)	0.138
Post-Research Activities	0.20 (2, 9.34)	0.818	1.03 (3, 7.76)	0.432

Notes: Groups

By Department: Elementary, Junior High School, Senior High School

By Length of Service: 0-1 year, 2-6 years, 7-11 years, 12 years and above (quartile-based)

Table 5: One-Sample Wilcoxon Sign Test for Relevance and Priority

	Median	Wilcoxon <i>W</i>	<i>p</i>
Relevance	4.86	153	<.001
Priority	5.00	153	<.001

Notes: Ho: $\mu \leq 3.5$

Discussion

Literature has emphasized the necessity for research-based needs assessments before spending resources on any professional development programs (60). In the present study, I explored the training needs of two schools at Napsan, Puerto Princesa, in an attempt to propose empirically-based

training themes aimed at enhancing their research capabilities.

The strong internal consistency across all training themes shows us the conceptual and statistical coherence of competencies within each domain, which reflects how the teachers at Napsan perceive these skills as inherently interconnected. For the Fundamentals training theme, the competencies

such as identifying research gaps, formulating research questions, and selecting theoretical frameworks are tightly interwoven that build sequentially toward establishing a robust research foundation mirroring pedagogical progression from problem formulation to hypothesis development (45). In Research Methods, the integration of selecting designs, applying methodologies, and integrating ethics highlights the holistic nature of methodological planning, where ethical alignment with sampling or mixed-methods strategies reflects inseparable best practices (44). The reclassification of the competency preparing interview scripts from Instrument Development ($\alpha = 0.83 \rightarrow 0.87$) to Qualitative Data Analysis ($\alpha = 0.94 \rightarrow 0.93$) revealed its misalignment with technical instrument validation and instead affirmed its role in pre-analytical workflows (48). The training theme of Quantitative Data Analysis demonstrates teachers' recognition of statistical literacy as a continuum, where descriptive statistics inform advanced analyses like ANOVA or factor analysis (39). Referencing training theme interlinks APA formatting, citation tools, and ethical paraphrasing, which reflects a framework for academic integrity (51), while Post-Research Activities unify dissemination strategies—publishing, policy briefs, and data archiving—into a cohesive phase of research impact. Collectively, these high internal consistencies validate the structural alignment of the framework with both theoretical models and practical workflows, which affirms competencies are logically grouped to address gaps holistically. Each training theme was rated on a scale of importance and proficiency, with the importance ratings (very important) indicating a strong consensus among teachers regarding the necessity of these skills for effective teaching and research. The significance of training and development competencies in enhancing professional effectiveness and addressing competency gaps in education has been re-emphasized (61). The proficiency ratings, however, tell a different story (moderately proficient). This disparity between the high importance ratings and the moderate proficiency ratings indicated a gap in teachers' skills that needs to be addressed. The gap has been found to be consistent with reported challenges from the

literature in acquiring the necessary competencies (62). Furthermore, the findings suggest that while teachers recognize the importance of these skills, they may lack the necessary training or resources to develop them effectively, a situation echoed in the literature on teacher training and professional development (63).

The teacher in the current study found all the training themes to be moderately needed. It is interesting that despite the zero-research output in 2023, they felt that these training themes were not critically needed at the moment. The theory of Planned Behavior posits that an individual's intention to perform a certain behavior (research) is contingent on their perceived attitude (importance), control (proficiency), and norm on the behavior (64). However, the current study was not able to explore the perceived norm of the teachers in doing research; thus, we can only speculate that the research culture in these schools is not institutionalized, and the school system might be lacking support or encouragement for teachers' research endeavors. This gap in understanding could be addressed in future research, as social norms could significantly influence educational practices (65). Unfortunately, the head teachers and the principals are not excluded from this phenomenon as they play a crucial role in shaping the research culture of their schools. A theoretical perspective that may explain this phenomenon is Bandura's social learning theory (66), which posits that individuals learn and adopt behaviors by observing and imitating the actions of those in influential positions. In this study, if teachers notice that their principals and head teachers are not engaged in research activities, they are likely to perceive research as an uncommon or unimportant practice within their institutional culture. In addition, the motivational theory of role modeling supports the claim that the absence of active research behavior among school leaders may lead teachers to question the value or relevance of investing their efforts in research, regardless of their own moderate proficiency in the necessary skills (67). In other words, when influential role models do not demonstrate engagement in research, it can have a cascading effect on the overall research output of the teachers, as the norms and expectations established

by leadership play a critical role in shaping professional behaviors.

The Instrument Development training theme stands out as the highest priority. This implies that while teachers recognize the important role of crafting, testing, and validating research instruments, they lack confidence in these essential skills. Seeking proficiency in this area could be crucial, as the literature indicates that difficulties in instrument development can undermine research outcomes, a point that resonates with our findings (68). Similarly, both Qualitative and Quantitative Data Analysis rank as major priorities; this signals that teachers feel significantly underprepared to handle the complexity involved in these essential research skills. Prior studies have echoed the importance of training in data analysis techniques, with a focus on building both competence and confidence for the teachers to successfully write research (69, 70). In contrast, though research fundamentals, methods, referencing, and post-research activities are also seen as important, gaps in these areas seem less urgent relative to the other training, perhaps due to a greater pre-existing competency. The literature discusses how effective professional development should address both pressing gaps and foundational skills, but the findings suggest that at this stage, educators may feel that the most immediate barrier lies in gaining proficiency in instrument development and data analysis rather than 're-strengthening' basic research foundations (71).

It was found that regardless of the organizational unit or the duration of a teacher's service, the gap between the importance assigned to research competencies and the self-assessed level of proficiency remains similar across all areas. This uniformity indicates that challenges in competencies such as instrument development, data analysis, and research methods are experienced broadly, a finding that resonates with other researchers, who argued that professional development needs are often widespread and not confined to specific subgroups (72). In addition, prior studies found that teachers across diverse contexts report comparable gaps in research-related skills, which supports the current observation that the need for improved research capacity is a common concern among educators regardless of departmental affiliation or years of

experience (73). These results imply that professional learning initiatives designed to strengthen research skills might be most effective when applied across the board rather than focused on particular groups. Such an approach may help address the pervasive disconnect between the high value that teachers place on these training themes and their confidence in executing them, which can ultimately contribute to a more research-engaged culture within these schools.

The validation of findings through community feedback is essential in educational research, particularly when assessing the relevance of training themes for teachers. The high median relevance and priority score achieved on the follow-up survey revealed that there is a strong consensus among teachers at Napsan on the necessity for these trainings, particularly in areas such as instrument development, quantitative analysis, qualitative analysis, post-research activities, fundamentals, and research methods. Community feedback is crucial for fitting educational programs to meet the specific needs of stakeholders (74). The findings emphasized the necessity of continuous dialogue between educators and the community to maintain the relevance and effectiveness of training programs.

Conclusion

The P-R-I-O-R-I-Ty framework seemed to have missed one important component, i.e., the subjective norms towards research. Hence, future adoption of this framework should include the measurement of perceived norms towards the activity. In addition, it was pointed out in the discussion section that perceived norms on conducting research might be playing a role in why, despite being reported that they are 'moderately proficient' in all training themes, they would not produce any research yet (this actually includes the heads and the principals of the said schools). Thus, beyond the training design, it is recommended that the principals (with the head teachers) actively encourage and model engagement in research activities. Leadership in research should be demonstrated through tangible actions such as conducting their own studies, supporting teacher-led research initiatives, and integrating research discussions into regular school meetings. School policies should also include structured incentives,

such as recognition programs, research allowances, and dedicated research time, to develop a positive research culture.

For the appropriate research training, since no differences were found in the needs of the subgroups, a unified teaching methodology and work examples must be given, i.e., the training methodology must not favor any subgroups. Ideally, all the proposed training themes must be implemented since all were classified as 'moderately needed.' However, if the funding agency has a limited budget, it should prioritize instrument development and quantitative analysis, among others. Moreover, the training program should be designed with an emphasis on hands-on, practice-based learning. Teachers should be guided through real-world research applications, such as conducting small-scale studies within their schools, developing and validating their own research instruments, and analyzing actual datasets. This experiential approach ensures that training is immediately relevant and applicable, which reinforces skill retention and confidence in research execution.

Finally, the institutionalization of mechanisms for sustained research engagement is deemed crucial. A Professional Learning Community (PLC) dedicated to research is to be established within these schools to provide ongoing support, mentorship, and opportunities for collaboration among teachers. Schools should seek partnerships with universities or research institutions to ensure continuous guidance and opportunities for professional development. It is suggested that the training program not conclude after four or five sessions, but rather that quarterly technical advisory meetings be held for at least one year to assist in the writing of their first research. Additionally, periodic follow-up assessments should be conducted to measure the impact of training interventions and identify emerging needs so that professional development efforts remain responsive to teachers' evolving research competencies.

Abbreviations

APA: American Psychological Association, DepEd: Department of Education, H_0 : Null hypothesis, NES: Napsan Elementary School, NNHS: Napsan National High School, RDM: Ranked Discrepancy Model, TNA:

Training Needs Assessment, WDS: Weighted Discrepancy Score, \bar{x} : Mean.

Acknowledgment

I would like to extend my sincere gratitude to the superintendent of the Schools Division of Puerto Princesa City for granting permission to conduct this study. I am also deeply thankful to the school principals of NES and NNHS for their unwavering support and to the teachers who participated.

Author Contributions

The author takes full responsibility for preparing the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest related to this work.

Declaration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Assistance

The author declare no use of artificial intelligence for the write-up of the manuscript.

Ethics Approval

The study followed strict ethical guidelines with voluntary, informed consent and approvals from the superintendent and school principals, ensuring confidentiality as required by the Philippine Data Privacy Act (RA 10173). It also adhered to a "No Disruption of Classes" policy, ensuring that no lessons were interrupted during data collection.

Funding

None.

References

1. Kincheloe J. Teachers as researchers. Classic ed. Routledge; 2012. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203801550>
2. Mai DT, Brundrett M. The importance of developing teachers as researchers in the new general education curriculum of Vietnam. *Manag Educ*. 2024;38(4):172-179.
3. Gironzetti E, Muñoz-Basols J. Research engagement and research culture in Spanish language teaching (SLT): empowering the profession. *Appl Linguist*. 2022;43(5):978-1005.
4. Caingcoy ME. Research capability of teachers: its correlates, determinants, and implications for continuing professional development. *J World Engl Educ Pract*. 2020;2(5):1-11.

- https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3631867
5. Gomez MA, Catan MM. Factors leading to limited researches conducted by Philippine public school teachers. *Innovare J Educ.* 2021;9(3):1-7.
 6. Codilla LL, Yangson-Barot H. Teachers as researchers: an emphasis on the readiness and attitude towards action research. *Int J Membr Sci Technol.* 2023;10(3):657-71.
<https://doi.org/10.15379/ijmst.v10i3.1586>
 7. Department of Education. DepEd Order 16, S. 2017 – Research management guidelines. 2017.
<https://www.deped.gov.ph/2017/03/20/do-16-s-2017-research-management-guidelines/>
 8. Department of Education. DepEd Order 24, S. 2010 - Basic education research fund. 2010.
<https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2010/03/DO-No.-24-s.-2010.pdf>
 9. Department of Education. DepEd Order 43, S. 2015 – Revised guidelines for the basic education research fund (BERF). 2015.
<https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/09/16/do-43-s-2015-revised-guidelines-for-the-basic-education-research-fund-berf/>
 10. Republic of the Philippines. Republic Act No. 10533: Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. May 2013.
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/rep-ublic-act-no-10533/>
 11. Grant J. Learning needs assessment: assessing the need. *BMJ.* 2002;324(7330):156-9.
 12. Soriano FI. Conducting needs assessments: A multidisciplinary approach. California: Sage Publications; 2013.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781506335780>
 13. Reyes-De Lana MS, Tanigue Y, Villa EB. Training needs assessment (TNA) of the women and children protection desk (WCPD) investigators: basis for a proposed enhancement program. *Int J Multidiscip Appl Bus Educ Res.* 2024;5(7):2687-715.
 14. Kaufman RA, English FW. Needs assessment: concept and application. Educational Technology Publications. 1979.
<https://books.google.com.ph/books?id=cs031o0SQC>
 15. Borich GD. A needs assessment model for conducting follow-up studies. *J Teach Educ.* 1980;31(3):39-42.
 16. Misanchuk ER. Analysis of multi-component educational and training needs. *J Instr Dev.* 1984;7(1):28-33.
 17. Abdel-Maksoud BM, Saknidy S. A new approach for training needs assessment. *J Hum Resour Sustain Stud.* 2016;4(2):102-9.
 18. Narine L, Harder A. Comparing the Borich model with the ranked discrepancy model for competency assessment: a novel approach. *Adv Agric Dev.* 2021;2(3):96-111.
 19. Choi HJ, Park JH. Exploring the viability of the ranked discrepancy model by comparing the weighted total index approach and the Borich model: a case of learning needs assessment of career guidance teachers. *Educ Sci.* 2023;13(4):414.
 20. Carifio J, Perla R. Resolving the 50-year debate around using and misusing Likert scales. *Med Educ.* 2008;42(12):1150-1152.
 21. Norman G. Likert scales, levels of measurement and the "laws" of statistics. *Adv Health Sci Educ.* 2010;15(5):625-32.
 22. Ku J, Han SH, Kang H. A structural analysis of adult learners' lifelong education consciousness, participation motivation, learning outcome. *J Korea Acad Ind Coop Soc.* 2015;16(7):4537-48.
 23. London M, Sessa VI, Shelley LA. Developing self-awareness: learning processes for self-and interpersonal growth. *Annu Rev Organ Psychol Organ Behav.* 2023;10:261-88.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-120920-044531>
 24. Luchman JN. Determining subgroup difference importance with complex survey designs: an application of weighted dominance analysis. *Surv Pract.* 2015;8(5). <https://doi.org/10.29115/SP-2015-0022>
 25. Bongco RT, Abenes R. Clash of spheres – the paradox of being a female teacher in the Philippines. *Beijing Int Rev Educ.* 2019;1(2-3):443-59.
 26. Sebastian M, Banate R, Saquin M. Gender roles among public elementary teachers: basis for gender-responsive intervention activities. *Int Online J Prim Educ.* 2022;11(2):401-11.
 27. Kline RB. Principles and practice of structural equation modeling. 4th ed. New York: Guilford Press; 2015.
<https://books.google.com.ph/books?id=Q61ECgAAQB-AJ>
 28. Hoe SL. Issues and procedures in adopting structural equation modelling technique. *J Quant Methods.* 2008;3(1):76-83.
 29. Singh K, Junnarkar M, Kaur J. Measures of positive psychology, development and validation. Berlin: Springer. 2016.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-3631-3>
 30. Edwards AA, Joyner KJ, Schatschneider C. A simulation study on the performance of different reliability estimation methods. *Educ Psychol Meas.* 2021;81(6):1089-1117.
 31. Park AR. Using factor analysis and Cronbach's alpha to ascertain relationships between questions of a dietary behavior questionnaire. *Agric Food Sci Educ.* 2007.
<http://www.asasrms.org/Proceedings/y2007/Files/JSM2007-000505.pdf>
 32. Grissom JA, Blissett RSL, Mitani H. Evaluating school principals: supervisor ratings of principal practice and principal job performance. *Educ Eval Policy Anal.* 2018;40(3):446-72.
 33. Zijlmans EAO, Tijmstra J, van der Ark LA, Sijtsma K. Item-score reliability in empirical-data sets and its relationship with other item indices. *Educ Psychol Meas.* 2017;78(6):998-1020.
doi: 10.1177/0013164417728358
 34. Slack N. The importance-performance matrix as a determinant of improvement priority. *Int J Oper Prod Manag.* 1994;14(5): 59-75.

35. Ting SH, Yahya S, Tan CL. Importance-performance matrix analysis of the researcher's competence in the formation of university-industry collaboration using Smart PLS. *Public Organ Rev.* 2020;20(2):249–75.
36. García-Fernández J, Fernández-Gavira J, Sánchez-Oliver AJ, Gálvez-Ruíz P, Grimaldi-Puyana M, Cepeda-Carrión G. Importance-performance matrix analysis (IPMA) to evaluate servicescape fitness consumer by gender and age. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(18):6562.
37. Chen SH, Pai FY, Yeh TM. Using the importance-satisfaction model and service quality performance matrix to improve long-term care service quality in Taiwan. *Appl Sci.* 2020;10(1):85. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10010085>
38. Tailab MMK. Using importance-performance matrix analysis to evaluate the financial performance of American banks during the financial crisis. *Sage Open.* 2020;10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020902079>
39. Strunk KK, Mwavita M. Design and analysis in educational research using jamovi: ANOVA designs. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003154297>
40. Canlas IP, Karpudewan M. Blending the principles of participatory action research approach and elements of grounded theory in a disaster risk reduction education case study. *Int J Qual Methods.* 2020;19:1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920958964>
41. Wagle SK, Luitel BC, Krogh E. Exploring possibilities for participatory approaches to contextualized teaching and learning: a case from a public school in Nepal. *Educ Action Res.* 2024;32(2):276–94.
42. Manakul T, Somabut A, Tuamsuk K. Smart teaching abilities of junior high school teachers in Thailand. *Cogent Educ.* 2023;10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2186009>
43. Punch KF, Oancea A. *Introduction to research methods in education.* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications; 2014. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1609406920958964>
44. Cohen L, Manion L, Morrison K. *Research methods in education.* Routledge. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315456539>
45. Creswell JW, Creswell JD. *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches.* Sage Publications; 2017. <https://edge.sagepub.com/creswellrd5e>
46. Haladyna TM, Rodriguez MC. *Developing and validating test items.* 1st ed. Routledge. 2013. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203850381>
47. Devellis RF, Thorpe CT. *Scale development: theory and applications.* 8th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications. 2022. <https://collegepublishing.sagepub.com/products/scale-development-5-269114>
48. Saldaña J. *The coding manual for qualitative researchers.* SAGE Publications. 2015. <https://study.sagepub.com/saldanacoding3e>
49. Harding J. *Qualitative data analysis: from finish to start.* 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications. 2019. <https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/asi/qualitative-data-analysis/book256252>
50. Richardson P, Machan L. *Jamovi for psychologists.* Bloomsbury Publishing. 2021. <https://www.bloomsbury.com/uk/jamovi-for-psychologists-9781352011852>
51. Landrum RE. *Undergraduate writing in psychology: learning to tell the scientific story.* Am Psychol Assoc. 2012. https://scholarworks.boisestate.edu/fac_books/337/
52. Kaur S, Dhindsa DK. Comparative study of citation and reference management tools: Mendeley, Zotero, and ReadCube. In: *Proc Int Conf ICT Bus Ind and Gov.* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICTBIG.2016.7892715>
53. Nguyen HB, Nguyen LT. Source-based academic writing through paraphrasing and summarizing: students' perceptions and practices. *Int J Innov Res Dev.* 2019;8(10):22-28. <https://doi.org/10.24940/ijird/2019/v8/i10/OCT19011>
54. Akbar MT. Students' paraphrasing in the literature review section of research proposal. *Jambura J Engl Teach Lit.* 2020;1(1):1–15.
55. Parija SC, Kate V. *Writing and publishing a scientific research paper.* Springer Singapore. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-4720-6>
56. Young J, Bridgeman MB, Hermes-DeSantis ER. Presentation of scientific poster information: lessons learned from evaluating the impact of content arrangement and use of infographics. *Curr Pharm Teach Learn.* 2019;11(2):204–10.
57. Leatham KR. Designing, conducting, and publishing quality research in mathematics education. Springer. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-23505-5>
58. Byman D. Writing policy recommendations for academic journals: a guide for the perplexed. *Int Secur.* 2024;48(4):137–66.
59. Macdonald K. Transforming your conference presentation into a journal article. *Partnership.* 2021;16(2):1-11.
60. Ferreira RR, Abbad G. Training needs assessment: where we are and where we should go. *Braz Admin Rev.* 2013;10:77–99.
61. Srimannarayana, M. Training and Development Competencies: A Comparative Study of Their Importance and Demonstration. *Journal of Management Research.* 2019; 11(3):1-17.
62. Alemu T. Perceptions of proficient English language users and learners with limited English language proficiency about the benefits of proficiency in English. *Ethiop J Bus Soc Sci.* 2019;2(1):28–52.
63. Arasomwan DA, Mashiya N. Foundation phase pre-service teachers' experiences of teaching life skills during teaching practice. *S Afr J Child Educ.* 2021;11(1):1-10.
64. Ajzen I. The theory of planned behavior. *Organ Behav Hum Decis Process.* 1991;50(2):179–211.
65. Singh YS, Singh KK, Singh CK. Understanding the attitudes of student-teachers in colleges of teacher

- education towards the teaching profession: a mixed-methods approach. *Educ Adm Theory Pract*. 2024;30(5):9463-73.
<https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i5.4134>
66. Bandura A. *Social learning theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall. 1977.
https://www.asecib.ase.ro/mps/Bandura_SocialLearningTheory.pdf
 67. Morgenroth T, Ryan MK, Peters K. The motivational theory of role modeling: how role models influence role aspirants' goals. *Rev Gen Psychol*. 2015;19(4):465-83.
 68. Elangovan N, Sundaravel E. Method of preparing a document for survey instrument validation by experts. *MethodsX*. 2021;8:101326.
 69. Setiawan I. Training on statistical data analysis techniques in classroom action research into scientific papers for teachers of SDN Inpres 2 Talise Palu City. *J Inovasi Sains Teknol Masyarakat*. 2024;2(2):59-67.
 70. Fajardo EG, Digo GS. Action research training: its effect on the research attitude, knowledge, and performance of teachers. *Jurnal Pendidikan Progresif*. 2023;13(2):329-46.
 71. Desimone LM. Improving impact studies of teachers' professional development: toward better conceptualizations and measures. *Educ Res*. 2009;38(3):181-199.
 72. Guskey TR, Sparks D. Linking professional development to improvements in student learning. In: Guyton E, Dangel JR, editors. *Research linking teacher preparation and student performance*. USA. Kendall/Hunt Publishing Company. 2002;12.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED464112.pdf>
 73. Darling-Hammond L. Research on teaching and teacher education and its influences on policy and practice. *Educ Res*. 2016;45(2):83-91.
 74. Mpuangnan KN, Ntombela S. Community voices in curriculum development. *Curr Perspect*. 2024;44(1):49-60.

How to Cite: Mark Donnel D Viernes. Research Training Needs Assessment of Teachers. *Int Res J Multidiscip Scope*. 2025; 6(4):41-56. doi: 10.47857/irjms.2025.v06i04.04536